

The Mathematics Education

ISSN 0047-6269

Volume - LV, No. 1, March 2021

Refereed and Peer-Reviewed Quarterly Journal

Journal website : www.internationaljournalsiwan.com

A Study of Exponential Functions of Operators such as Projection

by **Arbind Kumar**, *Research Scholar,*
Department of Mathematics,
Jai Prakash University, Chapra - 841301
E-mail : arbind841420@gmail.com

&

L.B. Singh, *Retd. Associate Professor,*
Department of Mathematics,
Jai Prakash University, Chapra - 841301
E-mail : lbsdmpu@gmail.com

Abstract :

In this paper, projection will be defined in a linear space. As Simmons G.F. "Introduction to topology and modern analysis." Projection is a linear operator A on a linear space such that $A^2 = A$, we defined e^A and leads to hyperbolic functions defined on A such as $\sinh A$, $\cosh A$, $\operatorname{sech} A$, $\tanh A$, and some interesting theorems.

Keywords : Linear space, Projection operator, Hyperbolic functions, Hilbert Space.

1. Introduction :

Projection Operator and Hyperbolic Functions :

Definition : Let L be a linear space⁶. Let A be a projection on L , then A is a linear transformation from L into L such that, $A^2 = A$ ⁷.

Define,

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^A &= I + A + \frac{A^2}{2!} + \frac{A^3}{3!} + \frac{A^4}{4!} + \dots \\
 &= I + A + \frac{A}{2!} + \frac{A}{3!} + \frac{A}{4!} + \dots \\
 &= I + A \left(1 + \frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{3!} + \frac{1}{4!} + \dots \right) \\
 &= I + A(e - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^{2A} &= (e^A)^2 = [I + A(e - 1)]^2 \\
 &= I + 2A(e - 1) + A^2(e - 1)^2 \\
 &= I + 2A(e - 1) + A(e - 1)^2 \\
 &= I + A(2e - 2 + e^2 - 2e + 1) \\
 &= I + A(e^2 - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, e^A is not a projection.

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^{3A} &= (e^A)^3 = (e^A)^2 \cdot e^A \\
 &= [I + A(e^2 - 1)] [I + A(e - 1)] \\
 &= I + A(e - 1) + A(e^2 - 1) + A(e^2 - 1)(e - 1) \\
 &= I + A(e - 1 + e^2 - 1 + e^3 - e^2 - e + 1) \\
 &= I + A(e^3 - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Assume,

$$e^{nA} = I + A(e^n - 1)$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^{(n+1)A} &= e^{nA} \cdot e^A \\
 &= [I + A(e^n - 1)] [I + A(e - 1)] \\
 &= I + A(e - 1) + A(e^n - 1) + A(e^n - 1)(e - 1) \\
 &= I + A(e - 1 + e^n - 1 + e^{n+1} - e^n - e + 1) \\
 &= I + A(e^{n+1} - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence by induction for any positive integers n ,

$$e^{nA} = I + A(e^n - 1)$$

If we put $n = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^{0A} &= I + A(e^0 - 1) \\
 &= I
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$e^0 = I, \text{ where } 0 \text{ is zero operator.}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &[I + A(e^{-n} - 1)] [I + A(e^n - 1)] \\
 &= I + A(e^n - 1) + A(e^{-n} - 1) + A(e^{-n} - 1)(e^n - 1) \\
 &= I + A(e^n - 1 + e^{-n} - 1 + e^0 - e^{-n} - e^n + 1) \\
 &= I + A(e^0 - 1) \\
 &= I
 \end{aligned}$$

So we can write inverse function

$$e^{-nA} = I + A(e^{-n} - 1)$$

Thus if n is a negative integer, then also,

$$e^{nA} = I + A(e^n - 1)$$

Hence for any integer n ,

$$e^{nA} = I + A(e^n - 1)$$

Let B be another projection, then

$$e^B = I + B(e - 1)$$

Then we find that,

$$\begin{aligned} e^A \cdot e^B &= [I + A(e - 1)] [I + B(e - 1)] \\ &= I + B(e - 1) + A(e - 1) + AB(e - 1)^2 \\ &= I + (A + B)(e - 1) + AB(e - 1)^2 \end{aligned}$$

We need $A+B$ to be a projection i.e,

$$\begin{aligned} (A+B)^2 &= A + B \\ \Rightarrow A^2 + 2AB + B^2 &= A + B \end{aligned}$$

Assuming A, B commute this is possible, when $AB = 0$.

Then,

$$e^A \cdot e^B = e^{A+B}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} e^{nA} \cdot e^{mB} &= [I + A(e^n - 1)] [I + A(e^m - 1)] \\ &= I + A(e^m - 1) + A(e^n - 1) + A(e^n - 1)(e^m - 1) \\ &= I + A(e^m - 1 + e^n - 1 + e^{n+m} - e^n - e^m + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= I + A(e^{n+m} - 1) \\
 &= e^{(m+n)A}
 \end{aligned}$$

I , identity operator is also a projection and

$$e^I = I + I(e - 1) = eI$$

$I - A$ is also a projection. Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^{I-A} &= I + (I - A)(e - 1) \\
 &= I + eI - I - eA + A \\
 &= eI + A(1 - e) \\
 e^A \cdot e^{I-A} &= e^{A+I-A} = e^I = eI
 \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^A \cdot e^{I-A} &= [I + A(e - 1)] [eI + A(1 - e)] \\
 &= eI + A(1 - e) + A(e - 1)e - A^2(e - 1)^2 \\
 &= eI + A(1 - e) + A(e - 1)e - A(e - 1)^2, \text{ As } A^2 = A \\
 &= eI + A(1 - e + e^2 - e - e^2 + 2e - 1) \\
 &= eI + A.0 \\
 &= eI
 \end{aligned}$$

2. We know that in a Hilbert space H , if P is a projection, then $P^2 = P$, $P^* = P$ and $P \geq 0$.

Theorem (2.1) : If A is a projection operator on a Hilbert space H^8 . Then e^A is non-singular.

Proof : We need to show that e^A or $I + A(e - 1)$ is one-to-one and onto as a mapping of H into itself. First we show that it is one-to-one.

Let $e^A x = 0$

$$\Rightarrow [I + A(e - 1)]x = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow x + (e - 1)Ax = 0$$

Applying A on both sides,

$$Ax + (e - 1)A^2x = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow Ax + (e - 1)Ax = 0, \quad \text{since } A \text{ is projection operator i.e. } A^2 = A$$

$$\Rightarrow eAx = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow Ax = 0$$

Hence

$$\Rightarrow x = 0$$

We next show that e^A is onto, i.e. its range is H . Let M be the range of e^A .

Let $x \in L$ then,

$$x + \left(\frac{1}{e} - 1\right)Ax \in L$$

Let $y = x + \left(\frac{1}{e} - 1\right)Ax \in L$

Then,

$$Ay = Ax + \left(\frac{1}{e} - 1\right)A^2x = Ax + \left(\frac{1}{e} - 1\right)Ax = \frac{1}{e}Ax$$

Consider $y + (e - 1)Ay$ or $e^A y$

Then,

$$y + (e - 1)Ay = x + \left(\frac{1}{e} - 1\right)Ax + \frac{e - 1}{e}Ax$$

$$= x + \left(\frac{1}{e} - 1\right)Ax + \left(1 - \frac{1}{e}\right)Ax = x$$

Thus, $x = e^A y$ i.e. $x \in M$

Hence, $L \subseteq M \subseteq L$ or $L = M$

Thus e^A is one-to-one and onto i.e. non singular.

3. Definition :

Next, we are going to define hyperbolic function involving a projection operator A .

Let $\cosh A = I + A(\cosh 1 - 1)$

$$= I + A \left(\frac{e + e^{-1}}{2} - 1 \right)$$

And $\sinh A = A \sinh 1 = A \left(\frac{e - e^{-1}}{2} \right)$

Hence, $\cosh A + \sinh A = I + A(e - 1) = e^A$

and $\cosh A - \sinh A = I + A(e^{-1} - 1)$

Hence, $\cosh^2 A - \sinh^2 A = [I + A(e - 1)] [I + A(e^{-1} - 1)]$

$$= I + A(e^{-1} - 1) + A(e - 1) + A(e - 1)(e^{-1} - 1)$$

$$= I + A(e^{-1} - 1 + e - 1 + 1 - e - e^{-1} + 1) = I$$

This is analogous to $\cosh^2 x - \sinh^2 x = 1$ when x is a real number.

We have seen before that,

$$e^{nA} = I + A(e^n - 1)$$

and $e^{-nA} = I + A(e^{-n} - 1)$

Adding,

$$\begin{aligned} 2\cosh nA &= 2I + A(e^n + e^{-n} - 2) \\ &= 2I + A(2\cosh n - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \cosh nA = I + A(\cosh n - 1) \quad (3.1)$$

Also subtraction gives,

$$e^{nA} - e^{-nA} = A(e^n - e^{-n})$$

$$\Rightarrow 2A\sinh n = A \cdot 2\sinh n$$

$$\Rightarrow \sinh nA = A\sinh n \quad (3.2)$$

Putting $n = -1$ in (3.1) and (3.2),

$$\begin{aligned} \cosh(-A) &= I + A[\cosh(-1) - 1] \\ &= I + A(\cosh 1 - 1) \\ &= \cosh A \end{aligned}$$

And $\sinh(-A) = A\sinh(-1) = -A\sinh 1 = -\sinh A$

Putting $n = 2$ in (3.2),

$$\sinh 2A = A\sinh 2 = A^2\sinh 1 \cosh 1 \quad (3.3)$$

Also $2\sinh A \cosh A = 2A\sinh 1(I + A(\cosh 1 - 1))$

$$= 2A\sinh 1 + 2A\sinh 1(\cosh 1 - 1)$$

$$= 2A\sinh 1 \cosh 1 \quad (3.4)$$

From (3.3) and (3.4),

$$\sinh 2A = 2\sinh A \cosh A$$

Theorem (3.I) : We show that,

$$\cosh 2A = \cosh^2 A + \sinh^2 A$$

Proof : Putting $n = 2$ in (3.1),

$$\cosh 2A = I + A(\cosh 2 - 1) \tag{3.5}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \cosh^2 A + \sinh^2 A &= [I + A(\cosh 1 - 1)]^2 + (A \sinh 1)^2 \\ &= I + A^2(\cosh 1 - 1)^2 + 2A(\cosh 1 - 1) + A^2 \sinh^2 1 \\ &= I + A[\cosh^2 1 + 1 - 2\cosh 1 + 2\cosh 1 - 2 + \sinh^2 1] \\ &= I + A(\cosh^2 1 + \sinh^2 1 + 1 - 2) \\ &= I + A(\cosh 2 - 1) \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

From (3.5) and (3.6),

$$\cosh 2A = \cosh^2 A + \sinh^2 A$$

Theorem (3.II) : Let us assume $AB = 0$.

Then we show that $\sinh(A + B) = \sinh A \cosh B + \cosh A \sinh B$

Proof : We have

$$\sinh(A + B) = (A + B)\sinh 1$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \sinh A \cosh B + \cosh A \sinh B &= (A \sinh 1)[I + B(\cosh 1 - 1)] + [I + A(\cosh 1 - 1)] B \sinh 1 \\ &= A \sinh 1 + B \sinh 1 \\ &= (A + B)\sinh 1 \\ &= \sinh(A + B) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem (3.III) : We show $\cosh(A + B) = \cosh A \cdot \cosh B - \sinh A \cdot \sinh B$

Proof : We have,

$$\begin{aligned} \cosh A \cosh B - \sinh A \sinh B &= [I + A(\cosh 1 - 1) - 1] [I + B(\cosh 1 - 1) - 1] \\ &\quad - (A \sinh 1)(B \sinh 1) \\ &= I + B(\cosh 1 - 1) + A(\cosh 1 - 1) \\ &= I + (A + B)(\cosh 1 - 1) \\ &= \cosh(A + B). \end{aligned}$$

4. Definition : Let us consider $I + A(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \cosh n A [I + A(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)] &= [I + A(\cosh n - 1)] [I + A(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)] \\ &= I + A(\operatorname{sech} n - 1) + A(\cosh n - 1) \\ &\quad + A^2(\cosh n - 1)(\operatorname{sech} n - 1) \\ &= I + A(\operatorname{sech} n - 1 + \cosh n - 1 \\ &\quad + 1 - \cosh n - \operatorname{sech} n + 1) = I \end{aligned}$$

Hence define,

$$\operatorname{sech} n A = I + A(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)$$

Define, $\operatorname{tanh} n A = \sinh n A \cdot \operatorname{sech} n A$

Theorem (4.I) : $\operatorname{tanh} n A = A \operatorname{tanh} n$

Proof : Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sinh n A \cdot \operatorname{sech} n A &= [A \sinh n] [I + A(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)] \\ &= A \sinh n + A^2 \sinh n (\operatorname{sech} n - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$= A \sinh n(1 + \operatorname{sech} n - 1)$$

$$= A \sinh n \operatorname{sech} n$$

$$= A \tanh n$$

Hence, $\tanh nA = A \tanh n$

Theorem (4.II) : $\operatorname{sech}^2 A + \tanh^2 A = I$

Proof : $\operatorname{sech}^2 A + \tanh^2 A$

$$= I + A(\operatorname{sech} 1 - 1)^2 + A^2 \tanh^2 1$$

$$= I + A^2(\operatorname{sech} 1 - 1)^2 + 2A(\operatorname{sech} 1 - 1) + A^2 \tanh^2 1$$

$$= I + A[\operatorname{sech}^2 1 + 1 - 2\operatorname{sech} 1 + 2\operatorname{sech} 1 - 2 + \tanh^2 1]$$

$$= I + A[\operatorname{sech}^2 1 + \tanh^2 1 + 1 - 2] = I + A(1 + 1 - 2) = I$$

Theorem (4.III) : $\tanh 2A(I + \tanh^2 A) = 2 \tanh A$

Proof : We have,

$$\tanh 2A = A \tanh 2$$

And, $I + \tanh^2 A = I + A^2 \tanh^2 1$

$$= I + A \tanh^2 1$$

Hence, L.H.S = $A \tanh 2(I + A \tanh^2 1)$

$$= \frac{A \cdot 2 \tanh 1}{1 + \tanh^2 1} (1 + A \tanh^2 1)$$

$$= \frac{A \cdot 2 \tanh 1 + A \cdot 2 \tanh^3 1}{1 + \tanh^2 1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{2A \tanh 1(1 + \tanh^2 1)}{1 + \tanh^2 1} \\ &= 2A \tanh 1 \\ &= 2 \tanh A \end{aligned}$$

References :

1. Chandra P. (2005) : International Journal of Mathematical Sciences, B.H.U., Varanasi, Vol. IV, No. 1, June.
2. Dunford, N. and Schwartz, J. (1967) : "Linear operators - part 1", Inter Science Publishers, Inc., New York.
3. Edward, R.E. (1965) : "Functional Analysis", Holt, Rinehart and Winston, Inc., New York.
4. Goffman, C. and G. Pedrick (1974) : "First course in functional Analysis", Prentice Hall, India, New Delhi.
5. L. Sternik L.A. and Sobolev V. J. (1961) : Element of functional Analysis (p. 36), Hindustan Publishing Corporation India.
6. Simmons, G.F. (1963) : Introduction to Topology and modern analysis, pp. 191-193.
7. Simmons, G.F. (1963) : Introduction to Topology and modern analysis, pp. 204-220.
8. Simmons, G.F. (1963) : Introduction to Topology and modern analysis, pp. 244-245.